

Probabilistic Design on Strength of Fiber Reinforced Composite Laminates

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ABSTRACT

This paper is concerned with the probabilistic design method for the strength of fiber-reinforced composite materials under the plane stress state. The proposed method accounts for the scatters of the material strength and the applied stress which is ignored in the conventional design approach. This method is established by applying the second-moment approximation method to the maximum stress criterion and the maximum work criterion. The fiber-reinforced laminate is treated as a homogeneous and orthotropic material. The presented method is applied to the laminate in on-axis and off-axis states. The computational procedure for obtaining the mean value of allowable applied stress is accomplished by using the input data as follows; (1) the mean value and the coefficient of variation of the material strengths in principal axes, (2) the coefficient of variation of applied stresses, (3) the angle between the load axis and the principal axis of material, (4) the probability of failure or the safety index.

INTRODUCTION

The fiber-reinforced composite materials are generally characterized by having considerable scatters in the mechanical properties. It is evident that these variabilities must be taken into account when these composites will be used as the structural materials. From this point of view, some probabilistic design methods considering the variation of the strength of composites have been proposed. (1,2) On the other hand, it is considered to be necessary to take the variation of applied load into consideration in the design of composite materials with reliability concept, since the variation of applied load can not be often ignored in comparison with that of the strength of composite.

This paper deals with the probabilistic design method for fiber-reinforced composite materials. The proposed method accounts for the scatters of the material strength and the applied load which are inclined to be ignored in the conventional design approach. Here, the fiber-reinforced composite laminate is treated as a homogeneous and orthotropic material. The two failure criteria, that is, the maximum stress criterion and the maximum work criterion, are applied to the composite laminate under on-axis and off-axis loadings. These criteria are widely used as the fracture theory of the fiber-reinforced composites. The probabilistic design method for the strength of the composite material under the plane stress state is established by applying the second-moment approximation method (3) to the

two failure criteria. The present method requires only the mean values and the coefficients of variation of both the principal strength components and the applied load. Thus, this method is considered to be simple and effective enough for practical use.

THEORY

In order to account for the behavior of the fiber-reinforced composites under combined stress states, we consider the homogeneous and orthotropic material of plane stress state under off-axis loading as shown in Figure 1. When 1-2 are the axes of material symmetry, and x-y are the reference coordinate axes of the externally applied stresses, the usual transformation equation in matrix form is

$$\begin{Bmatrix} s_1 \\ s_2 \\ s_6 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1^2 m^2 & -2lm \\ m^2 l^2 & 2lm \\ 1m & -1m (1^2 - m^2) \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} s_x \\ s_y \\ s_\theta \end{Bmatrix} \tag{1}$$

,where $m = \cos\theta$, $n = \sin\theta$ and θ is the angle between the applied stress and principal axes. On-axis loading is contained in off-axis as a special case of $\theta = 0$. s_1, s_2 and s_6 are the stress components with respect to the material principal axes and s_x, s_y and s_θ are those of the load axes. S_1, S_2 and S_6 are strength components at the principal axes as shown in Figure 2. When s_1 and/or s_2 are compressive, the corresponding compressive strengths are required. In this paper, we choose the maximum stress and the maximum work criteria which are most common failure criteria for composite materials. The probabilistic design methods for composite materials based on the these failure criteria are proposed.

Maximum Stress Criterion

This criterion specifies that failure of composite material results when one of applied stresses reaches the corresponding strength without regard to the other stresses. Therefore, this theory is described by the following inequalities.

$$Z_{m1} = S_1 - s_1 < 0, \quad Z_{m2} = S_2 - s_2 < 0, \quad Z_{m6} = S_6 - s_6 < 0 \tag{2}$$

,where $Z_{mi} (i=1,2,6)$ denote safety margins.

The S-S model (Stress-Strength model) shall be introduced for a probabilistic design approach. The concept of this model is that the stress introduced by operating conditions and the strength of material are treated as random variables and if the applied stress exceeds the strength of material failure results as shown in Figure 3. As $S_i (i=1,2,6)$ denote the strength random variables and $s_i (i=1,2,6)$ the stress random variables, the safety margins, Z_{mi} , also become to be random variables from Eq.(2).

The probabilities of failure for each principal direction, P_{fi} , are given by

$$P_{fi} = \text{Prob.} [Z_{mi} < 0] = G_{Z_{mi}}(0) \quad (i=1,2,6) \tag{3}$$

,where $G_{Z_{mi}}$ show the distribution functions of Z_{mi} . Using the relation of $\xi = (z - \mu_z) / \sigma_z$, Eq.(3) may be transformed as follows;

$$P_{fi} = G_{\xi_{mi}} \left(-\frac{\mu_{Z_{mi}}}{\sigma_{Z_{mi}}} \right) \quad (i=1,2,6) \tag{4}$$

,where μ and σ are the mean and the standard deviation for the subscript, respectively. The relation of $Q_{mi} = \mu_{Z_{mi}} / \sigma_{Z_{mi}}$ and use of Eq.(4) lead to the following equation.

$$Q_{mi} = -G_{\xi_{mi}}^{-1}(P_{fi}) \quad (i=1,2,6) \tag{5}$$

Q_{mi} are called as the safety index and are used as a measure of reliability. When the distribution function, $G_{\xi_{mi}}$, is known, Q_{mi} is obtained from P_{fi} . By use of first order approximation, the mean and the standard deviation of safety margins are calculated as

$$\mu_{Z_{mi}} = 1 - P_{fi}, \quad \sigma_{Z_{mi}} = \sqrt{C_{S_i}^2 + F_i^2 C_{s_i}^2} \quad (i=1,2,6) \tag{6}$$

,where C is the coefficient of variation for subscripts. F_i denote the reciprocals of central safety factor shown as follows;

$$F_i = \mu_{s_i} / \mu_{S_i} \quad (i=1,2,6) \tag{7}$$

Using the first order approximation, the transformation equation with respect to the mean values of applied stresses is given by

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mu_{s_1} \\ \mu_{s_2} \\ \mu_{s_6} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & m & -21m \\ m & 1 & 21m \\ 1m & -1m & (1^2 - m^2) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mu_{s_x} \\ \mu_{s_y} \\ \mu_{s_s} \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

In the same manner as the mean value of applied stress, the transformation equation for the variations of applied stresses is given by

$$\begin{pmatrix} C_{s_1}^2 \\ C_{s_2}^2 \\ C_{s_6}^2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & m & -1m \\ m & 1 & 21m \\ 1m & -1m & (1^2 - m^2) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} C_{s_x}^2 \\ C_{s_y}^2 \\ C_{s_s}^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Thus, the probability of failure for composite materials in the case of the maximum stress criterion is described as

$$P_f = 1 - (1 - P_{f1}) (1 - P_{f2}) (1 - P_{f6}) \quad (10)$$

Maximum Work Criterion

Tsai and Wu has proposed a general failure theory which may cover various theories based on the maximum work criterion. (4) The form of failure criterion for the composite material under plane stress loading is described as

$$Z = 1 - \left[\frac{1}{S_1} \left(s_1 \left(\frac{1}{S_1} - \frac{1}{S_1'} \right) + \frac{s_1^2}{S_1 S_1'} + \frac{s_2^2}{S_2^2} + \frac{2k_{12} s_1 s_2}{\sqrt{S_1 S_1' S_2 S_2'}} \right) \right] \leq 0 \quad (11)$$

, where S_i, S_i' ($i=1,2$) are the tensile and compressive strengths at principal axes, respectively. k_{12} is the interaction term and the absolute value of k_{12} is less than unity. The failure of the composite material is assumed to occur if Z_e in Eq.(11) is negative. Substituting Eq.(1) into Eq.(11), it follows that Z_e is the function of $s_x, s_y, s_s, S_1, S_1', S_2, S_2'$ and S_6 . These variables are assumed to be independent random variables. By expanding Eq.(11) in a Taylor series about the mean of each variable and using the first order approximation, the mean value of Z_e is given by

$$\mu_{Z_e} = 1 - \left[\left(1 - \frac{1}{r_{\mu 1}} F_1 + \left(1 - \frac{1}{r_{\mu 2}} \right) F_2 + \frac{1}{r_{\mu 1}} F_1^2 + \frac{1}{r_{\mu 2}} F_2^2 + \frac{2k_{12}}{\sqrt{r_{\mu 1} r_{\mu 2}}} F_1 F_2 \right) \right] \quad (12)$$

Similarly, the variance of Z_e is shown as

$$\sigma_{Z_e}^2 = (C_{s_x} \tau_x)^2 + (C_{s_y} \tau_y)^2 + (C_{s_s} \tau_s)^2 + C_{S_1}^2 (\tau_1^2 + r_{C1} \tau_1'^2) + C_{S_2}^2 (\tau_2^2 + r_{C2} \tau_2'^2) + (C_{S_6} \tau_6)^2 \quad (13)$$

, where $r_{\mu i}$ and $r_{C i}$ are described by

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \mu_{S_i}' &= r_{\mu i} \mu_{S_i} \\ C_{S_i}' &= r_{C i} C_{S_i} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (i=1,2,6) \quad (14)$$

and

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} \tau_x \\ \tau_y \\ \tau_s \end{aligned} \right\} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\mu_{s_x}^2}{\mu_{s_1}^2} & \frac{\mu_{s_x}^2}{\mu_{s_2}^2} & \frac{\mu_{s_x}^2}{\mu_{s_6}^2} \\ \frac{\mu_{s_y}^2}{\mu_{s_1}^2} & \frac{\mu_{s_y}^2}{\mu_{s_2}^2} & \frac{\mu_{s_y}^2}{\mu_{s_6}^2} \\ \frac{\mu_{s_s}^2}{\mu_{s_1}^2} & \frac{\mu_{s_s}^2}{\mu_{s_2}^2} & \frac{\mu_{s_s}^2}{\mu_{s_6}^2} (1^2 - m^2) \end{pmatrix} \left\{ \begin{aligned} (\tau_1 + \tau_1') \\ (\tau_2 + \tau_2') \\ \tau_6 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (15)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \tau_1 &= F_1 + \frac{1}{r_{\mu 1}} + \frac{k_{12}}{\sqrt{r_{\mu 1} r_{\mu 2}}} F_1 F_2, \quad \tau_6 = 2F_6^2 \\ \tau_1' &= -\frac{1}{r_{\mu 1}} + \frac{1}{r_{\mu 1}} + \frac{k_{12}}{\sqrt{r_{\mu 1} r_{\mu 2}}} F_1 F_2 \\ \tau_2 &= F_2 + \frac{1}{r_{\mu 2}} + \frac{k_{12}}{\sqrt{r_{\mu 1} r_{\mu 2}}} F_1 F_2 \\ \tau_2' &= -\frac{1}{r_{\mu 2}} + \frac{1}{r_{\mu 2}} + \frac{k_{12}}{\sqrt{r_{\mu 1} r_{\mu 2}}} F_1 F_2 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (16)$$

For the special case of unidirectional loading of the laminate with the off-axis state, the variation of Z_e is simplified as

$$\sigma_{z_e}^2 = C_{s_x}^2 (\zeta_1 + \zeta_1' + \zeta_2 + \zeta_2' + \zeta_6)^2 + C_{s_1}^2 (\zeta_1^2 + r_{c1}^2 \zeta_1'^2) + C_{s_2}^2 (\zeta_2^2 + r_{c2}^2 \zeta_2'^2) + C_{s_6}^2 \zeta_6^2 \quad (17)$$

, and then σ_{z_e} is reduced as in the case of $\theta=0$

$$\sigma_{z_e}^2 = C_{s_x}^2 (\zeta_1 + \zeta_1')^2 + C_{s_y}^2 (\zeta_2 + \zeta_2')^2 + C_{s_s}^2 \zeta_6^2 + C_{s_1}^2 (\zeta_1^2 + r_{c1}^2 \zeta_1'^2) + C_{s_2}^2 (\zeta_2^2 + r_{c2}^2 \zeta_2'^2) + C_{s_6}^2 \zeta_6^2 \quad (18)$$

Thus, the probability of failure based on the maximum work criterion is calculated by

$$p_f = \text{Prob.} \{Z_e < 0\} = G_{Z_e}(0) = G_{\xi_e} \left(-\frac{\mu_{z_e}}{\mu_{z_e}} \right) \quad (19)$$

If p_{fa} is the allowable probability of failure, the non-destructive condition of composite materials is

$$\frac{\mu_{z_e}}{\sigma_{z_e}} > -G_{\xi_e}^{-1}(p_{fa}) = Q_{ea} \quad (20)$$

, where Q_{ea} is the safety index corresponding to the allowable probability of failure.

COMPUTATIONAL PROCEDURE

The structural design of the composite materials may often have the procedure to determine the dimensions of the component such as cross-sectional area, thickness, etc., when the characteristics of the applied load and the strength of the material are given. Such procedure reduces to the problem to determine the allowable stress applied to the component.

First, the flow chart for obtaining the mean value of allowable applied stress in the case of the maximum stress criterion is shown in Figure 4. The input data necessary to the present procedure are as follows; (1) the mean values and the coefficients of variation of the material strengths in the principal axes, (2) the coefficients of variation of applied stresses, (3) the angle between the load axis and the principal axis of material and (4) the probability of failure. p_{f1} , p_{f2} and p_{f6} satisfying Eq.(10) are computed in the range not greater than 0.5, since the values of safety factor should be greater than unity. Using Eqs.(5),(6) and (8), we can obtain the every sets of μ_{s_x} , μ_{s_y} and μ_{s_s} having the given probability of failure.

Secondly, the flow chart for the computational procedure based on the maximum work criterion is shown in Figure 5. In this case, the input data are the same as the case of the maximum stress criterion. μ_{s_x} , μ_{s_y} and μ_{s_s} with the initial values of zero are increased gradually by increments of the small values of $\Delta\mu_{s_x}$, $\Delta\mu_{s_y}$ and $\Delta\mu_{s_s}$, respectively. The judgement whether or not the non-destructive condition of Eq.(20) is satisfied is made for each set of mean values of applied stresses. Thus, the range of the mean values of allowable applied stresses is decided under the given probability of failure.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES AND CONSIDERATIONS

The proposed probabilistic design method is applied to the unidirectional glassfiber-reinforced epoxy laminate. The experimental data of on-axis and off-axis loading used in the present study are quoted from the paper by Tsai.(5) The mean values and the coefficients of variation of the normal strengths (S_1 , S_1' , S_2 and S_2') and the shear strengths (S_6) of the laminate are illustrated in Table 1. The data with respect to the coefficient of variation in this table are obtained from Jone's data.(6)

First, the mean values of the allowable applied stresses are calculated for the laminate under on-axis loading. The numerical results by the computational procedure based on the maximum stress criterion are shown in Figure 6. The design tolerance region of on-axis state is shown with the probability of failure and the coefficient of variation of applied stress as parameters. The three reciprocals of central safety factor in principal axes, F_1 , F_2 and F_6 are adopted as the coordinate axes, respectively. In this calculation, the various values represented in the Table 1 are used as the strengths of the laminate, and the distribution func-

tion of safety margin is assumed to be the normal distribution. It is found in this figure that the curved surface of failure has a tendency to decrease as the probability of failure decreases and the coefficient of variation of applied stress increases. It should be noted that the mean values of applied stresses have to be estimated at smaller value as the scatters of applied stresses increase even if the probability of failure is constant.

Next, the numerical results in the case of the maximum work criterion are illustrated in Figure 7. Comparing this figure with Figure 6, it is found that the curved surfaces of failure are more conservative than those of the case of the maximum stress theory, since it is generally known that the results obtained by substituting unity into the interaction term, k_{12} , lead to the most conservative values.

The calculated results for the unidirectional laminate under the uniaxial loading are shown in Figures 8 and 9. In both figures, the ordinate is the mean value of allowable applied stress and the abscissa is the angle between load axis and the principal axis. These results are obtained by the computational procedure based on the maximum work criterion. This calculation is carried out as a special case of $\mu_{S_y} = \mu_{S_x} = 0$ and $C_{S_y} = C_{S_x} = 0$ in the flow chart of Figure 7, and the variance of Z_e is obtained by use of Eq.(17). Figure 8 shows the comparison of the allowable tensile stress (solid line) and compressive stress (dotted line) with the experimental data by Tsai, where a parameter is the probability of failure. The variance of applied stress (s_x) is treated as zero, since the scatter of the applied stress is left of account. It is observed in this figure that the mean value of the applied stress decreases as the angle in abscissa increases, and the calculated results have good agreement with the experimental data for the tensile stress but comparatively good for the compressive stress. Figure 9 shows the effect of the coefficient of variation of applied stress (C_{S_x}) on the mean value of the applied stress (μ_{S_x}). It is found that μ_{S_x} decreases as C_{S_x} increases.

The numerical results for the unidirectional laminate under the on-axis state and the uniaxial loading are illustrated in Figure 10. This figure shows the relation between F_1 and the safety index with C_{S_x} as a parameter. It is indicated that the central safety factor should be estimated largely as the safety index and the variation of the applied stress increase. After all, it should be noted from the various results described above that the mean value of applied stress or the central safety factor must be decided by taking the scatters of the applied stress and the material strength and the given probability of failure into account.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, a probabilistic design method for the strengths of fiber-reinforced composite materials under the plane stress state has been proposed. The present method is characterized by that both the scatters of the material strength and the applied stress are considered. This design method is accomplished by applying the second-moment approximation method to the maximum stress criterion and the maximum work criterion. The computational procedures for obtaining the mean value of the applied stress or the central safety factor of principal axes are described in the cases of two criteria. It is concluded from the numerical results that the mean values of applied stresses or the central safety factors of the uniaxial axes have to be decided by taking the scatters of the applied stress and the material strength and the probability of failure into account. The present method is considered to be effective for practical use, since it requires only the mean values and the variations of both the material strength and the applied stress.

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Figure 1. Relation between principal axis and load axis.

Figure 2. Explanation of symbols on the principal axis of laminate and applied stress.

Figure 3. Explanation of S-S model.

Table 1. The data of unidirectional glassfiber-reinforced composite.

Strength of laminate	Mean μ (Mpa)	Coefficient of variation C (%)
Tensile strength (S_1)	1032.9	10.0
Compressive strength (S_1')	1032.9	12.0
Tensile strength (S_2)	27.4	11.0
Compressive strength (S_2')	137.2	8.0
Shear strength (S_6)	54.9	6.0

Figure 4. Flow chart for obtaining the mean values of applied stresses in the case of the maximum stress criterion.

Figure 5. Flow chart for obtaining the mean values of applied stresses in the case of the maximum work criterion

Figure 7. The tolerance region of design for the unidirectional laminate in on-axis based on the maximum work criterion.

Figure 6. The tolerance region of design for the unidirectional laminate in on-axis based on the maximum stress criterion.

Figure 10. Relation between safety index and F_1 based on the maximum work criterion in the case of only applied stress s_1 under on-axis loading.

Figure 8. Relation between the mean value of allowable applied stress and loading angle with the probability of failure as a parameter in the case of the maximum work criterion

Figure 9. Relation between the mean value of allowable applied stress and loading angle with the coefficient of variation of applied stress as a parameter in the case of the maximum work criterion.